

Supplementary Figure 2. Characterisation of clonal PICs. (A) Morphology of 7 PIC clones observed using light microscopy. Scale =200 μ m. (B) Flow cytometric analysis of PW1 expression in the 7 clonal PIC populations. (C) Flow cytometric analysis of Sca-1 expression in the 7 clonal PIC populations.